

Semantic maps of causation:

What different data types and methods can (and cannot) tell us

Abstract

The present paper discusses connectivity and proximity maps of causative constructions. In the first part, we show that creation of a connectivity map of causatives is not a trivial task due to incomplete descriptions, inconsistent terminology and the problem of determining the semantic nodes, and propose an innovative data-driven solution based on data from a parallel corpus. The second part of the paper focuses on proximity maps based on Multidimensional Scaling and compares the most important semantic distinctions, which are inferred from typological data and from a parallel corpus of film subtitles. The results suggest that corpus-based maps of tokens are more sensitive to cultural differences in the prominence of specific causation scenarios, such as interpersonal letting and forceful causation, than maps based on constructional types, which are described in reference grammars.

Keywords: causation, Multidimensional Scaling, graph theory, cluster analysis, parallel corpus

1. Aims of this paper

Semantic maps serve three main purposes. First, they can represent co-verbalization patterns in a particular semantic or pragmatic domain and predict the synchronic and diachronic variation of linguistic expressions. These are the main goal of connectivity semantic maps (van der Auwera 2013) in which related semantic or pragmatic functions (uses, meanings, etc.) are linked in a graph in the most parsimonious way.

The second purpose is to reveal cross-linguistically predominant semantic or pragmatic distinctions and clusters of functions that are frequently expressed by the same constructions in different languages. This information can be inferred from probabilistic proximity maps, which are usually based on corpora. On such maps, the proximities between individual corpus instances represent the chances of these contexts being expressed by similar linguistic forms (Wälchli & Cysouw 2012; Author XXXX).

Finally, semantic maps provide a convenient tool for comparison of semantically related constructions in different languages. Both connectivity and proximity maps can be used for this purpose.

The present paper deals with all these tasks and discusses different types of maps of causative constructions. Causation is a semantic domain which includes diverse situations where one participant of an event expressed by a clause brings about a physical or mental

change in another participant (or at least has an opportunity of doing so). Consider an example in (1):

(1) *Harry Potter made the chair levitate.*

In this sentence, Harry Potter is the Causer, and the chair is the Causee. The causing event is something that Harry did (e.g. using a levitation charm), and the caused event is that the chair levitated as a result of Harry's actions.

Causation can be expressed by various causative constructions – e.g. lexical (*break*), morphological (e.g. *solidi-fy*) or periphrastic/analytic (e.g. *make X disappear*). This semantic domain has been extensively studied in linguistic typology and in functional and cognitive linguistics (e.g. Comrie 1981; Kemmer & Verhagen 1994; Song 1996; Dixon 2000; Talmy 2000; Shibatani & Pardeshi 2002). Numerous semantic distinctions and categories have been discussed. For example, causation can be direct or indirect, forceful or natural, intentional or accidental, factitive or permissive.

Despite that, we still do not have a detailed and empirically supported connectivity map of causative constructions. Given the massive amount of studies, this may seem surprising. However, if one considers the reasons below, one can easily understand why creating a semantic map of causatives is by no means a trivial task.

The first problem is the divergent terminology used by the authors of grammars and research articles. One of the problematic cases is direct and indirect causation (cf. Shibatani & Pardeshi 2002). These labels have been used to refer to numerous closely related distinctions. One of them is spatiotemporal integration of causing and caused events (Comrie 1981; Haiman 1983; cf. Fodor 1970). Another is whether the Causer is the main source of energy for the caused event or some other entity or force (e.g. Kemmer & Verhagen 1994). Although in most cases these distinctions would overlap, this is not always so. For example, a patient with a paralyzed hand can request the nurse to help him unlock his mobile phone and get some important information. According to the spatiotemporal integration criterion, this would be an instance of direct causation by the patient because his thumb would touch the screen, while the main source of energy criterion would say that the patient is not the main source of energy, and therefore the causation is indirect.

At the same time, other labels have been used to refer to very similar distinctions, such as distant vs. contact causation (Nedjalkov & Silnicky 1973) or manipulative vs. directive causation (Shibatani & Pardeshi 2002). This inconsistency makes the cross-linguistic comparison of causatives a difficult task.

The second problem is the focus of most grammar descriptions on the most typical factitive implicative causation (i.e. making something happen or someone do something) and scarce information about the other types: permissive, accidental curative, assistive, directive, non-implicative, etc. Many grammars describe the default causative construction simply as a means of increasing the valency of a verb, without referring to its semantic functions.

The third, and less obvious, problem is that causative constructions are usually described in terms of salient distinctive features. For example, one can often find in a grammar a statement that construction A expresses direct causation, while construction B expresses indirect causation. Leaving aside the terminological issues, the problem here is that direct and indirect causation do not represent some kind of semantic primitives and can be further divided into many subtypes. For example, indirect causation can be permissive, i.e. causation by letting X do something (*I let her read the novel*) or factitive (e.g. *I had him read the novel*), while direct causation may be forceful (e.g. *I pried the door open*) or not (e.g. *I opened the door with a key*). Both direct and indirect causation can be intentional (e.g. *I opened the door a little in order to hear the conversation* [direct, intentional] or *I had the butler open the door* [indirect, intentional]) or not intentional (e.g. *Children can open the door accidentally* [direct, not intentional] or *I caused the door to open by conjuring a wrong charm* [indirect, not intentional]), and so on. The number of distinctions mentioned in the descriptions of causatives in different languages is very high (see Section 3.1).

This focus on one or two salient dimensions represents a problem for creation of semantic maps because their nodes are semantic functions, or uses, such as Recipient or Direction for dative constructions (Haspelmath 2003) or Specific Unknown and Specific Known for impersonal pronouns (Haspelmath 1997). These functions are verbalized in communication on their own. In contrast, distinctive binary (or tertiary, etc.) features cannot be verbalized on their own, but only in bundles. This makes the study of co-verbalization of causatives tricky.

To solve this problem, we could come up with an etic grid which contains all possible combinations of distinctive features (cf. Evans 2010), described and illustrated in a very transparent way. Since the grammars do not describe the semantic range of causatives in sufficient detail (see Section 3.1), one would need to fill in a questionnaire. One should keep in mind, though, that the number of nodes would be high. For example, if we take 7 binary distinctions, the total number of combinations to describe would be $7^2 = 49$. Obviously, it is a challenge to obtain this information for different constructions. In addition, due to the strong correlations between the features (Author XXXX), some of the configurations will be unlikely to occur in the real world. As an illustration, consider forceful indirect physical causation, where the Causer exerts extra effort in order to affect the Causee indirectly. One could only think of an example from fantasy. Fans of the trilogy *Lord of the Rings* might remember the episode when the wizard Gandalf uses all his magic forces to stop the Balrog, a demon shrouded in fire, in the Mines of Moria. Language users or experts would have problems with such items in a questionnaire because these situations are beyond their language experience.

The present paper offers a practical, data-driven solution of these problems. The data are taken from a parallel corpus. This allows us to avoid the problem of missing descriptions and conflicting labels. The semantic functions, which serve as the nodes, are not pre-determined in advance, but emerge as clusters from individual causation events. The clustering enables us to avoid the proliferation of nodes.

As already mentioned, the second purpose of semantic maps is identification of cross-linguistically salient semantic distinctions and clusters of semantic functions or exemplars. There has been some research in this direction. For instance, Author (XXXX) shows that a

crucial distinction made by European analytic causatives is the contrast between factitive causation (‘making’) and permissive causation (‘letting’). The present paper focuses on all types of causatives constructions (analytic, lexical and morphological) and typologically diverse languages. Moreover, it compares two sources of data: descriptions in grammars and research articles, and parallel corpora. The question is, do the most important distinctions depend on the type of data, and, if yes, how can we explain these differences?

The remaining part of the paper is as follows. Section 2 describes the data-driven approach, which allows us to infer the nodes for a connectivity map of causation. In Section 3, I compare the salient semantic contrasts based on parallel corpus tokens and descriptions of causative constructions provided in reference grammars and research papers. Section 4 discusses the results and their implications.

The statistical analyses discussed below were performed with R, a free statistical software and programming environment (R Core Team 2018), and add-on packages *cluster* (Maechler et al. 2018), *igraph* (Csardi & Nepusz 2006) and *smacof* (de Leeuw & Mair 2009). The datasets and R code can be found in the supplementary materials.

2. Towards a data-driven connectivity map of causatives

2.1. Data from a parallel corpus

This section outlines a data-driven approach to creating connectivity maps based on a parallel corpus. I used data from a corpus of film subtitles. All subtitles were collected from the website *opensubtitles.org*. The advantage of this type of data is its closeness to spontaneous informal discourse (Author XXXX). Most of the subtitles were aligned with the subtitles in English with the help of software *subalign* (Tiedemann 2012).

For this pilot study, I took 18 causative situations from the English subtitles of the film *Avatar* (2009), more exactly, its first half. The list of situations, which were selected randomly, is given in Table 1. Many instances of direct factitive causation expressed by lexical causatives (e.g. *kill*, *cut*, *break*) were ignored because this is by far the most common and cross-linguistically uniform type of causation. Some situations were discarded because they had no causative constructions in the translations.

Next, I found manually the constructions that express these causation events in 22 languages, including the English version. The majority are Indo-European languages: Germanic (English, Danish, Dutch, German, Swedish), Romance (French, Portuguese, Romanian, Spanish) and Slavic (Bulgarian, Czech, Polish and Russian). The non-Indo-European languages are Uralic (Estonian, Finnish and Hungarian), Hebrew, Indonesian, Mandarin Chinese, Thai, Turkish and Vietnamese.

Table 1. List of causation events and their short labels.

English sentence	Short label
Let's go special case, do not make me wait for you.	You_make_me_wait
As head of security, it is my job to keep you alive.	I_keep_you_alive
Plus it'll help keep (you sane).	It_HELPS_keep_you_sane
(Plus it'll help) keep you sane.	It_helps_KEEP_you_sane
Just relax and let your mind go blank.	Let_your_mind_go_blank
You're wiggling your toes!	You_wiggle_toes
This low gravity will make you soft.	Gravity_makes_you_soft
(They could fix me up, if I rotated back.) Make me pretty again.	They_make_me_pretty
It reminds me every day what's waiting out there.	It_reminds_me_of_X
Just keep your mouth shut (and let Norm do the talking).	Keep_mouth_shut
(Just keep your mouth shut and) let Norm do the talking.	Let_him_do_talking
Relax marine, you're making me nervous.	You_make_me_nervous
Norm, you've contaminated the sample with your saliva.	You_contaminate_sample
Why not let them just kill my ass?	Let_them_kill_my_ass
Who gets them to move?	Who_gets_them_to_move
So just find me a carrot that will get them to move.	Carrot_gets_them_to_move
You may tell her what to do, inside.	You_tell_her_what_to_do
I'm not about to let Selfridge and Quaritch micromanage this thing.	I_let_SMB_micromanage_thing

The translations found in the subtitles were analysed and coded as different types of causative constructions. All lexical causatives were treated as one constructional type. Morphological causatives were distinguished depending on the suffix, e.g. Indonesian has causative verbs with the suffixes *-kan* and *-i*, e.g. *meng-hamil-kan* and *meng-hamil-i*, which both mean 'make pregnant' (Sneddon 1996: 97). Such examples were treated as different constructions. Analytic causatives were distinguished by the verb that expresses the abstract causing event. For example, French causatives *faire* + Infinitive and *laisser* + Infinitive were treated as separate constructions. A non-trivial question is how fine-grained the classification should be. For example, one may wonder whether to treat *make* + *Verb* and *make* + *Adjective* as one or two constructions. In the European languages, where adjectives and verbs are easy to distinguish, I treated such constructions as separate types, while in the South-East Asian languages, where this distinction is not obvious, they were considered one type. Also, finite and non-finite predicates specifying the caused event were treated differently in those languages where one could make this distinction. Versions of causative verbs with and without prefixes were treated as one construction, e.g. Indonesian (*mem*)*buat* 'make' + Predicate. The marking on the Causee and word order patterns were disregarded. Of course, the problem of deciding what constitutes a separate construction is by no means limited to corpus data. When relying on grammars, we "outsource" the decision to the author, which does not make the issue any less problematic.

The result of this analysis was a matrix of language-specific constructions (rows) and causation events (columns). A fragment is shown in Table 2. In this table, '1' means that this

construction was used to express the causation event in the corpus, whereas ‘0’ means that this construction was not used to express this causation event.

Table 2. Matrix of constructions and causation events: a fragment.

Language	Construction	You_make_me_wait	I_keep_you_alive	It_HELPS_keep_you_sane
ENG	make_Vinf	1	0	0
ENG	keep_Adj	0	1	0
ENG	help_Vinf	0	0	1
ENG	let_Vinf	0	0	0
ENG	make_Adj	0	0	0
ENG	Lex	0	0	0
ENG	get_toVinf	0	0	0
ENG	tell_toVinf	0	0	0
RUS	zastavljat_Vinf	1	0	0
RUS	pomogat_Vinf	0	0	1
RUS	Lex	0	0	0
RUS	derzhat_Adj	0	0	0

2.3. Identification of nodes

In order to identify more abstract semantic functions, which can serve as the nodes of a semantic map, the causation events were clustered according to how they are expressed in the languages. First, a distance matrix of the situations was created based on the similarity measures. The values in the table were treated as binary asymmetric, which means the following. If two causation events were expressed with the same construction in a given language, the similarity score was increased by 1. If not, nothing was added. The sum similarity between the events was then divided by the total number of comparisons between the causation events where at least one value was non-zero. This proportion is also known as Jaccard similarity coefficient J . The similarity scores were transformed into distances by subtracting the former from 1: $D = 1 - J$. After that, a standard agglomerative cluster analysis was performed using the average method of aggregation. Figure 1 displays the clustering tree.

Figure 1. Cluster analysis of 18 causation events.

The figure displays seven clusters, delimited by red rectangles. Why was this number chosen? One can determine the optimal number of clusters using so-called average silhouette widths. The higher the silhouette width, the better the clustering solution. A good solution means that the members of the clusters are maximally close to one another and at the same time maximally distant from the members of the other clusters. Figure 2 shows the silhouette widths for the number of clusters from 2 to 10. The plot suggests that the optimal number of clusters is 7.

Figure 2. Average silhouette widths for different number of clusters.

The clusters in Figure 1 can be interpreted as follows, moving from left to right:

- TELL: mandative, or directive, non-implicative causation (*You tell her what to do*), which is only represented by one context. Non-implicative means that it is not clear whether the caused event took place or not (Karttunen 1971). Note that this type of causation does not overlap formally with any other causation events. All other examples represent implicative causation.
- KEEP: keeping the animate or inanimate Causee in a particular state, by a human or some circumstances;
- MAKE_X: the animate or inanimate Causer intentionally or accidentally makes the Causee change its state. The Causee in the examples is animate, but affected by the Causer.
- NO_CONTROL_CE: somebody or something brings about the change in the Causee, which has no control over the process;
- HELP: only one example, where something helps to keep someone in a certain state;
- LET: causation of non-interference (Talmy's 2000 non-impingement) of the Causer in the action performed by the Causee;
- CONTROL_CE: indirect factitive (i.e. not permissive) causation in which the Causee has control over the caused event. The Causer can be animate or inanimate, acting intentionally or not intentionally.

Let us now consider more closely the neighbouring clusters with MAKE_X and NO_CONTROL_CAUSEE. The formal difference between them is that MAKE_X is expressed in many languages as a verb of making followed by an adjective. As for NO_CONTROL_CAUSEE, most languages express these types with lexical causatives (with some exceptions, such as the English original *Let your mind go blank*, which corresponds to a lexical causative in some other languages). This explains why these two semantic types do not form one big cluster. This formal difference can be explained by the differences in usage frequencies (Haspelmath 2008). Lexical causatives are usually more frequent than analytic ones. Language users exhibit communicatively efficient behaviour, choosing shorter words to express frequent causation events, and leaving more cumbersome analytic structures for less frequent events (Author XXXX). Since frequency differences are not relevant for semantic maps, these two functions can be merged. In what follows, the label NO_CONTROL_CAUSEE will also cover the cluster MAKE_X.

2.4. Automatic creation of the semantic map

After the clusters were identified, the original construction-event matrix was recoded. The columns were now the six big clusters described above (where MAKE_X is treated as an instance of NO_CONTROL_CAUSEE due to the reasons outlined above). If a construction was used to express at least one event from a cluster, it received 1. Based on this matrix, we can finally build the semantic map. For this purpose, I used the software created by Regier et al. (2013).¹ Their Python script, which builds parsimonious semantic maps from a matrix of linguistic forms and semantic functions, is based on an efficient algorithm for the social network inference problem proposed by Angluin et al. (2010). The result is shown in Figure 3. The position of TELL, which has no co-expression links, was chosen arbitrarily.

¹The Python code can be found at <http://lclab.berkeley.edu/regier/semantic-maps/> (last access July 9 2019).

Figure 3. Semantic map of causatives. CE stands for Causee.

Figure 4 demonstrates how the language-specific constructions map onto the resulting graph. Note that the lone node TELL is not displayed. The largest semantic area belongs to the Chinese analytic causative *ràng* + Predicate. As shown in Figure 4a, it has all semantic functions with exception of KEEP. It is followed by the Indonesian analytic causative (*mem*)*buat* + Predicate, which was attested in the clusters KEEP, NO_CONTROL_CAUSEE and CONTROL_CAUSEE (see Figure 4b). KEEP and NO_CONTROL_CAUSEE are found in many lexical causatives: Bulgarian, Danish, German, Hebrew, Indonesian and Romanian, as shown in Figure 4c. The combination of NO_CONTROL_CAUSEE is found in numerous constructions: Finnish and Turkish morphological causatives, Portuguese *fazer* + Infinitive, Vietnamese analytic causative with *làm*, and lexical causatives in Finnish, Hungarian, Russian and Thai (Figure 4d). NO_CONTROL_CAUSEE and LET are co-expressed by the English *let* + Infinitive, Indonesian *biarkan* + Predicate, Portuguese *deixar* + Infinitive and Finnish *antaa* + Infinitive (Figure 4e). LET and CONTROL_CAUSEE co-occur in the Dutch *laten* + Infinitive and Thai *hai* + Predicate (Figure 4f). The remaining constructions have only

been observed in one function and therefore do not contribute anything to the map.

Figure 4. Semantic configurations of different language-specific constructions.

The map allows us to make some predictions. In particular, a causative construction that expresses KEEP is unlikely to express LET if it does not express direct factitive causation NO_CONTROL_CE. Similarly, HELP cannot be co-expressed with the factitive causation functions if LET is not expressed, as well. As for TELL, it is likely to be merged with the rest of the map when more data are added. The reason is the fact that some languages develop an implicative causative from originally non-implicative constructions with directive semantics (i.e. order/ask/tell X to do Y). An example is Polish *kazać*, which means ‘say, tell’, but which can be also used implicatively, as in (2):

- (2) *Kazał-Ø* *na* *siebie* *długo czekać*.²
 say.PST-3SG.M on self.ACC long wait
 ‘He made (others) wait for himself for a long time.’

It is most likely that TELL will be merged with CONTROL_CE first because the addressee of a request or order can decide whether to comply with the Causer’s demands or not.

Obviously, this is only a first step towards building a data-driven link map of causative constructions. We need more different sources of data, more non-European languages and more causative situations to cluster.

3. In search for salient semantic contrasts

3.1. Typological data

3.1.1. Typological data

Causation is a standard item on the to-do list of grammarians who plan to describe a language. However, there are a few serious problems with the existing descriptions, which were discussed in Section 1. This type of data is not entirely useless for semantic maps, however. We can focus on the cross-linguistically salient distinctions, as done in previous token-based proximity maps (see Section 1). Which types of causation are usually expressed by different constructions, and which by similar ones in languages of the world? We will use a popular dimensionality reduction technique, Multidimensional Scaling (MDS) (e.g. Croft & Poole 2008; Wälchli & Cysouw 2012). This procedure will help us visualize the distinctions that are most typical in languages of the world.

² <https://sjp.pwn.pl/szukaj/kaza%C4%87.html> (last access 08.07.2019)

More than 200 reference grammars were analysed for this case study. From those, descriptions of 142 causative constructions were obtained which satisfied two criteria. First, there was a semantic description. Second, each of the languoids belonged to a unique genus, according to the classification given in the online World Atlas of Language Structures (Dryer & Haspelmath 2013). These constructions represent 62 languoids and therefore 62 genera.

The semantic descriptions had very diverse semantic categories, which were classified into several larger superordinate categories, as shown in Table 3. This generalization was a necessary step. Without it, we would not be able to compare the constructions cross-linguistically. Note that some of the features have their opposites in the descriptions (e.g. DIRECT vs. INDIRECT), whereas the others do not (e.g. PORTATIVE or ASSISTIVE).

Table 3. Semantic distinctions found in grammars and their superordinate categories (in capitals).

DIRECT direct, contact, manipulative, non-mediated, causer as the main source of energy or controller responsible on the caused event, focus on the effect on the Causee, integrated cause and effect, physical contact between the Causer and Causee, the Causee is affected, direct personal involvement of the Causer; describes what happens to the Causee, not what he/she does; affected Causee	INDIRECT indirect, distant, roundabout or ‘indefinite’ causation, the events are weakly or not (necessarily) integrated spatiotemporally; “X arranged the matter so that Y happened”, interpersonal causation
INTENTIONAL intentional or purposeful causation, volitional or agentive instigator/Causer	NOT INTENTIONAL accidental, unintentional
ASSISTIVE assistive; the causer is in the position of caring for, chaperoning, or helping the Causee	
CURATIVE curative, have something done by someone	
NO CONTROLLING CAUSEE non-controlling, non-volitional or passive Causee, the Causee’s volition or choice is downgraded, the Causee is affected, has no causal agency	CONTROLLING CAUSEE the Causee is active and controlling; the Causee performs some action, has a degree of autonomy, interpersonal causation
IMPLICATIVE	NON-IMPLICATIVE
COMITATIVE comitative, sociative or involved causation; the causer performs or experiences the action or state he/she/it initiates, participating to some degree in the joint activity	
NOT FORCEFUL non-forceful, mild, effortless or neutral causation, cause something without resistance	FORCEFUL forceful causation, forcing, causation by force
COMMUNICATION causation with the help of (verbal) communication: directive, mandative (command, ordering, compelling, persuading), rogative (asking), invitation	
FACTITIVE factitive or coercive causation, making	PERMISSIVE permissive causation, letting, can express ‘allow’
CAUSED STATE causation of a state	CAUSED ACTION
PORTATIVE portative	
PUTTING	

causation as putting in a certain position	
TOTALLY AFFECTED CAUSEE total affectedness of the object	
INTENSIVE intensive	
MOVING CAUSEE moving Causee or liquid	
DOUBLE CAUSATION three-participants causation	

In addition to that, the following features were added to the data based on conceptual considerations:

- Permissive causation was also coded as indirect;
- Mandative/directive and curative causation were also coded as indirect and with a controlling Causee;
- Forceful causation was treated as factitive (not permissive);
- Portative causation (carry X to some place) was treated as comitative (i.e. involving the Causer who also performs the caused event): by carrying or bringing something to a certain location, the Causer also moves there;
- Causation with a controlling Causee is indirect (with the exception of assistive causation);
- Double causation (e.g. X causing Y to do X) is treated as indirect.

3.1.2. Semantic map based on MDS

In order to obtain stable results, all rare features that occur in less than 5 constructions were removed. Also, all constructions in which only one feature is observed, were disregarded because they do not contribute anything to the distances between the semantic features. The resulting matrix with data constituted 98 rows (language-specific constructions) and 18 columns (semantic features). The excluded features were PORTATIVE, PUTTING, DOUBLE CAUSATION, TOTALLY AFFECTED CAUSEE, MOVING CAUSEE. They can be considered *rara* in the domain of causation, based on this representative cross-linguistic sample.

The presence of a feature in the semantic range of a construction was coded as 1, and its absence was coded as 0. These values were treated differently, i.e. the data were binary asymmetric (see an explanation of this term in Section 2.3). The reason is that the absence of a feature (0) in a construction's description may be due to missing information or due to a genuine absence of this function in the semantic repertoire of the construction. In most cases, we cannot tell. So, when two features have 0 in one construction and 0 in another one, we cannot treat that as a sign of correlation between the features. Similarity is only established when both features have 1 in both constructions.

Next, I performed MDS based on stress minimization using majorization (de Leeuw & Mair 2009), which produces low stress – a standard measure of goodness of fit of an MDS solution. The default ratio scaling method was used. I tested several solutions with a different

number of dimensions and chose the solution with three dimensions as the optimal one. The stress of the 3D solution was 0.21. Adding the 4th dimension did not lead to an interpretable map and a large decrease in stress.

The existing analytical tools for MDS allow us to investigate which of the points are poorly represented by the map. A stress plot suggests that Forceful and Curative are the features whose distances to the other points are the least reliably fitted by the MDS. However, none of the features is responsible for more than 8% of the total amount of stress, which means that none of the features has a very poor fit.

The resulting MDS is shown in Figure 5, from two different perspectives.

Figure 5. A 3D MDS map based on typological data from different perspectives. Top: dimensions 1 and 2; bottom: dimensions 2 and 3.

Looking closely at the 3D map, we can interpret the dimensions as follows. The first dimension (horizontal) stretches from comitative/assistive/curative causation on the left to permissive causation on the extreme right. This contrast can be interpreted as agentive involved Causer vs. non-involved Causer. It also correlates with direct (left) vs. indirect causation (right). The second dimension contrasts implicative causation at the back with non-implicative causation in the very front, which often goes with causation by communication (i.e. directive, mandative, etc. causation). Finally, the third dimension places forceful causation at the bottom and non-forceful at the very top. Forceful causation is always factitive, but non-forceful is usually associated with communication, assistance, curative causation and caused actions where the Causee is an agent.

3.2. Parallel corpus

3.2.1. Corpus of film subtitles

This section presents an MDS map based on data from parallel corpora. For this case study, I used again a corpus of film subtitles. There were five films of different genres:

- *Avatar* (action, adventure, fantasy, 2009)
- *Black Swan* (drama, thriller, 2010)
- *Frozen* (animation, adventure, comedy, 2013)
- *Noah* (action, adventure, drama, 2014)
- *Twilight* (drama, fantasy, romance, 2008)

As in the case study discussed in Section 2, the subtitles were collected from the website *opensubtitles.org* and aligned with the English version. In addition to English, nine other languages from different genera were investigated: Finnish, French, Hebrew, Indonesian, Mandarin Chinese, Russian, Thai, Turkish and Vietnamese.

As a starting point, 182 contexts were found in the English version, which represent diverse causative events (factitive and permissive, implicative and non-implicative, assistive, curative, etc.). The constructions expressing these events were identified in each of the languages. See more information about the coding in Section 2.1.

Consider an example. One of the contexts in *Avatar* was *Don't shoot, you'll piss him off*. The causative event was *SMB pisses SMB off*. In English, the construction was encoded as a lexical causative. In French, the translation was *Vous allez l'énerver*, which also contains a lexical causative. The Turkish translation was *Onu kızdıracaksınız*, where the verb *kızdır-* is a morphological causative derived from *kız-* 'lose one's temper'. The Vietnamese version contained an analytic causative with the auxiliary *làm* 'make'.

- (3) *Cậu sẽ làm nó nổi điên đó.*
 you will make him become mad there
 'You'll cause him to get mad.'

Table 4. Data from the parallel corpus: a fragment.

Film	Context	RUS	FIN	FRA	THA	VIE	TUR
Avatar	They can fix the spine, if you got the money.	Lex	Lex	Lex	Lex	Lex	Morph
Avatar	Let's go special case, do not make me wait for you.	zastavljat_V	Morph	faire_V	hai_Pred	đề_Pred	NA
Avatar	...that will stop your heart in one minute.	Lex	Morph	NA	Lex	NA	Morph
Avatar	As head of security, it is my job to keep you alive .	NA	pitää_V	NA	NA	NA	Pred_tutmak
Avatar	It's nothing like an old school safety brief to put your mind at ease .	Lex	Lex	mettre_PP	Lex	NA	NA
Avatar	Me and Norm here, are to drive these remotely controlled bodies called avatars.	Lex	Lex	Lex	Lex	Lex	Lex
Avatar	but you can take them out tomorrow.	Lex	Lex	NA	Lex	Lex	NA

The result of this time-consuming procedure, in which I relied on numerous reference grammars and online translation tools, was a matrix with the causation events as rows and the languages as columns. The cells contained the construction types. See a fragment of the table in Table 4. If a non-causative periphrastic expression was used or the translation was incomplete or erroneous (in rare cases), the label NA (not available) was added.

3.2.2. MDS map

Based on the matrix described in the previous section, I created a matrix of distances between the causative events. The distances were computed as follows. If two causative events had the same constructions within one language, 1 was added to their similarity score. The sum similarity score was then divided by the total number of comparisons without missing data. Finally, the proportion was subtracted from one.

As in the previous case, solutions with the number of dimensions 2, 3 and 4 were tested. The solution with 3 dimensions was optimal, with the stress value of 0.16. Adding the fourth dimension would only reduce the stress by 3%, which is a very small improvement. Interpreting an MDS map with corpus tokens is always a difficult task. In order to do it, the causation situations were coded for the same features as in the previous case study. Next, I used linear regression analysis in order to identify which of the semantic variables are the most strongly correlated with the coordinates of the causative events on the three dimensions of the MDS model. The measure was adjusted R^2 , which is the standard way of representing the relative strength of relationship between two variables in linear regression. The procedure has already been used by Author (XXXX) for similar purposes. The coefficients are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Adjusted R^2 of the linear regression on the coordinates of each dimension.

Semantic distinction	Dimension 1	Dimension 2	Dimension 3
Intentional or Not	-0.004	0.071	0.032
Forceful or Not	0.011	0.004	-0.005
Comitative or Not	0.003	-0.004	0.001
Direct or Not	0.191	-0.004	0.000
Causee Control or No Control	0.203	-0.001	0.015
Factitive or Permissive	0.520	0.158	0.045
Caused Event or State	0.290	-0.003	0.012
Implicative or Not	0.021	-0.006	0.037
Assistive or Not	0.019	0.022	0.147
Curative or Not	0.005	-0.005	-0.005
Directive or Not	0.021	-0.006	0.038

The coefficients reveal that the first dimension is associated the most strongly with the distinction between factitive and permissive causation (i.e. making vs. letting), followed

by the features related to (in)directness of causation and the role of the Causee. The second dimension is also correlated with factitive vs. permissive causation, and to some extent with the distinction between intentional and non-intentional Causer. Figure 5 displays the 1st and 2nd dimensions of the MDS model, which show that the permissive events form a separate cluster in the top left corner. Note that the dense cluster on the right corresponds to direct factitive causation, usually expressed by lexical causatives (and sometimes morphological ones). Finally, the third dimension reveals a contrast between assistive (i.e. helping) and non-assistive causation due to the cluster of situations related to helping at the bottom of Figure 6, which shows the second and the third dimension.

Thus, different types of data yield different salient semantic dimensions. In particular, the distinction between factitive and permissive causation is very prominent in the corpus – a contrast we do not clearly observe in the typological data. This may be explained by two reasons. First, according to Wierzbicka (2006: Section 6.2.3), letting is an important category in the Anglo-Saxon culture because it is associated with non-interference, non-imposition and personal freedom. In addition to ‘normal’ letting as absence or cessation of impingement, e.g. *I let him enter/escape/stay*, one can also find instances of interpersonal letting in the data, where the verb *let* is used to regulate human interaction. These uses can be classified into several types:

- *let* of permission, i.e. not preventing the Causee from doing what he or she intends to do, e.g. *I’ll let you tag along* (Frozen);
- *let* of shared information, e.g. *Let me know if that's juicy enough for you* (Black Swan);
- *let* of tolerance, e.g. *So I’ll let you finish. Bye* (Black Swan);
- *let* of cooperative dialogue, e.g. *Let me make this very important announcement* (Black Swan);
- *let* of cooperative interaction, e.g. *Let me take you to Noah* (Noah).

According to Wierzbicka (2006: 187), these uses “acknowledge the rights of the addressee as an autonomous and free individual, on equal footing with the speaker”.

This prominence of letting in the English data may have impact on its frequency in the other languages, which often use periphrastic causatives with verbs of permission to translate *let* of non-interference (in particular, permission and tolerance). For instance, *I’ll let you finish* is translated by a construction with the verb *dat’* ‘give’ in Russian, *antaa* ‘let’ in Finnish, *để* ‘let’ in Vietnamese, etc. The example of *let* of cooperative interaction *Let me take you to Noah* is translated into some languages by a verb of letting, e.g. French *Laissez-moi vous emmener voir Noé*, which may not be the best choice. Such translationese effects may increase the influence of the making vs. letting distinction on the geometry of the MDS solution. At the same time, many of the other instances of cooperative letting are not expressed by such constructions. For instance, the above-mentioned example of *let* of cooperative dialogue *Let me make this very important announcement* is translated into French as *J’ai une annonce très importante à faire!* ‘I’ve got an important announcement to make!’. The request for shared information *Let me know* is translated mostly by lexical verbs of saying or telling. These choices are idiomatic.

Another important reason for the absence of a prominent contrast between factitive and permissive causation in the typological data may be the predominant focus of the grammarians on factitive causation as the ‘default’. It can be explained by stereotypes of what constitutes causation proper, as well as by the higher level of grammaticalization of the more frequent ‘making’ in comparison with the relatively infrequent ‘letting’. As a result, the grammarians may not regard permissive causation as a part of grammatical system, leaving it for the lexicon.

Unlike in the typological data, we do not find a clear contrast between forceful and non-forceful causation in the corpus – probably because this type of causation is rare in the films and in our everyday life, thanks to different machines, gadgets and social institutions. There can be a cultural difference between different languages, as far as the prominence of physical effort is concerned. In the post-industrial societies, physical violence and hard physical work are exceptions, rather than the rule.

Figure 5. MDS based on corpus data: dimensions 1 and 2.

Figure 6. MDS based on corpus data: dimensions 2 and 3.

4. Conclusions and implications

This paper has demonstrated that creation of a connectivity map of causatives is not a trivial task. The reasons are the focus of grammars on the most salient distinctive features, the terminological confusion and the incomplete descriptions of causatives. The paper has also shown how one can solve these problems with the help of a data-driven approach, using data from a parallel corpus and inferring the nodes as clusters of individual causative events. We hope that future research will enrich this preliminary map with new functions and links between them.

The second important goal of semantic maps is to find salient semantic contrasts between different types of causatives. The comparison of MDS based on typological and parallel corpus data (Section 3) has revealed that the salient distinctions vary. This may have to do with the sparse descriptions in the grammars, in particular, the focus on the highly grammaticalized ‘default’ causative forms, which usually express factitive implicative

causation. The differences may also be due to cultural factors. According to Wierzbicka (2006), the Anglo-Saxon culture emphasizes the importance of non-interference, non-imposition and negative freedom, which can be regarded as negative politeness. This explains why English has a variety of constructions with interpersonal *let* (Wierzbicka 2006: Section 6.2.3). The high frequency of permissive causation in the English version of the film subtitles may explain why the contrast between factitive and permissive causation is very strong in the corpus data, and weak in the typological data. Moreover, forceful causation is less important in the highly industrialized cultures than in other societies, which explains why there are few tokens of this type in the corpus data and therefore no evidence that this distinction is important, unlike in the typological data. In general, one would expect corpus-based semantic maps with usage tokens to be more prone to predominant cultural scenarios than maps based on constructional types. Therefore, it would be worthwhile to look at different pivot languages, films from other countries and other genres of text in the future.

From all this follows that one should be extremely careful when trying to interpret a semantic map as representing some ‘universal’ conceptual space. A universal space presupposes the same dimensions. However, we have seen that they may differ substantially depending on the type of data.

Finally, the results of this study have implications for the description of causatives in reference grammars. The authors should be encouraged to focus on more dimensions of causation than simply (in)directness and related distinctions. In addition, it would be very useful to create a common metalanguage of causative semantics and avoid the terminological inconsistency in the description of causatives.

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